

INSTRUMENTATION OF MODERN TOOLS OF MANAGEMENT CONTROL BY CAMEROONIAN PUBLIC HOSPITALS

INSTRUMENTATION DES OUTILS MODERNES DU CONTRÔLE DE GESTION PAR LES ÉTABLISSEMENTS PUBLICS HOSPITALIERS CAMEROUNAIS

Didier AKAMBA MVOMO, PhD.

Senior Lecturer

Faculty of Applied Economics and Management

University of Douala, Cameroon

didierakamba_mv@yahoo.fr

Joseph Herman TIONA WAMABA, PhD.

Senior Lecturer

Research Laboratory on Corporate Governance and Performance

Advanced Teachers Training College for Technical Education

University of Douala, Cameroun

wambanadal@gmail.com

Annick ATSAIN, PhD.

University of Jean Lorougnon-Guédé de Daloa (UJLOG)

Ivory Coast

atsaina75@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The aim of this article was to assess the extent to which modern tools of management control are used in Cameroon's public hospitals. The article main question being framed as follows: is modern management control a reality in Cameroonian hospitals? As such, we reviewed the literature on the implementation of management control in public hospitals. The methodological approach being the quantitative approach, we built a questionnaire as data collection tool. The questionnaire helped us to collect data which was analyzed using the SPSS and SmartPLS software for the purpose of longitudinal analyses and structural equation modeling respectively. The main result of this article states that Cameroon's public hospitals make good use of modern tools of management control. While the scores of the various indicators of all the axes of the balanced scorecard are high, only one indicator named "increased revenues" presents a fair but not so high coefficient.

Key-words : Management control; Modern tools of management control; Traditional tools of management control; Instrumentation; Public Hospitals

ABSTRACT

L'objectif de cet article est d'évaluer le degré d'utilisation des outils modernes de contrôle de gestion dans les hôpitaux publics camerounais. La question principale de cette communication étant la suivante : le contrôle de gestion moderne est-il une réalité au sein des établissements hospitaliers publics au Cameroun ? Pour ce faire, nous avons réalisé une revue de l'essentiel de la littérature sur la mise en œuvre du contrôle de gestion dans les hôpitaux publics. L'approche méthodologique étant l'approche quantitative, nous avons donc construit un questionnaire comme outil de collecte de données. Les données collectées ont été analysées à l'aide des logiciels SPSS et SmartPLS aux fins d'analyses longitudinales et de modélisation par équations structurelles respectivement. Le principal résultat de cet article atteste que les hôpitaux publics du Cameroun utilisent bel et bien des outils modernes de contrôle de gestion. Alors que les scores des différents indicateurs de tous les axes du tableau de bord prospectif sont élevés, seul un indicateur nommé « augmentation des revenus » présente un coefficient mitigé.

Mots-clés : Contrôle de gestion, outils modernes de contrôle de gestion, outils traditionnels de contrôle de gestion, instrumentation, hôpitaux publics.

INTRODUCTION

Public hospitals are traditionally subject to two constraints: quality of care and budgetary constraints. Management control meets the imperatives of corporate performance (Avele D. and Bikourane N., 2017). As a result, hospital managers need to implement a dynamic approach focused on efficiency to optimize funds. In the same vein, Anthony (1988) shows that management control is a process by which managers influence other members of the organization to implement action plans. Current developments in the control of public companies suggest that the administrative cordon linking public companies to the State is being broken. This trend could give rise to the risk of abuse, arbitrariness or even fraud. For this reason, Poyet M. (2001) stresses that the institutions that control public enterprise are still very useful in legitimizing it. According to this author, these checks confer a certain legitimacy on the actions of the public enterprise, which might be tempted to evade them because of its corporate nature, and the control of the public enterprise as a check and balance therefore seems to make good sense.

However, more than any other entity, today's public enterprise has two seemingly antagonistic objectives to follow: the satisfaction of the general interest and the pursuit of profit. However, analysis shows that the State manages to reconcile these two aims by imposing the general interest as a public power and by taking into account the profitability of the public company by granting it greater management autonomy (Durupty M., 1984). The ultimate aim of controlling public enterprise is not to choose between these two objectives, but to channel the factors which influence them. This is where new public management (NPM) comes into play as the framework for applying management control to public enterprise. Underperformance in the public sector was due to centralised bureaucracy, ineffective control mechanisms and wasteful use of available resources. These, then, are the problems that New Public Management is trying to tackle. New public management marks the transition from traditional public administration to new public management, an administration in which management control has a major role to play.

The main question of this paper is as follows: is modern management control a reality in Cameroonian hospitals? In other words, what is the level of use of modern management control tools in hospitals in Cameroon?

In order to answer this question, this article reviews the main literature on management control and its tools (I); then, by clarifying the methodological approach and the data collection and analysis tools (II), we present the results of this article (III). These results are then discussed (IV).

1. LITERATURE REVIEW

1.1. A conceptual approach to management control

Controlling a situation means being able to master it and steer it in the desired direction. The aim of any control is to measure the results of an action and to compare these results with the objectives set a priori to determine whether they match or they diverge.

According to Alfred Chandler (1962), management control is a tool for "coordinating, judging and planning". For Henri Bouquin (1994), management control comprises the systems and processes that ensure consistency between strategy and concrete, day-to-day actions. Robert Anthony (1965) defines management control as

"a process by which managers obtain assurance that resources are obtained and used effectively and efficiently to achieve the organization's objectives". This definition places particular emphasis on the rational use of resources facilitated by management control. This is also the case with the definition of Khemakhem (1976), according to whom management control is the process implemented within an economic entity to ensure the effective and permanent mobilization of energies and resources with the aim of achieving the entity's objective.

Thus, the definition that seems to reconcile all the above pioneering definitions is the following: management control is a set of procedures whose purpose is to enable management to ensure that objectives are achieved efficiently, i.e. by making the best use of the scarce resources. This definition, which we describe as "neutral", can be adapted to all organizations depending on their objectives. For private companies, the objective of management control is to support the achievement of maximum profit; whereas for public companies, it is to support the maximization of user's satisfaction.

1.2. Theoretical approach to management control within public companies

Current developments in the control of public companies tend to show a break in the administrative cordon that links public companies to the State. This trend could give rise to the risk of abuse, arbitrariness or even fraud. For this reason, Poyet M. (2002) stresses that the institutions that control public enterprises are still very useful in legitimizing them. For the same author, these counter-powers confer a certain legitimacy on the actions of the public enterprises, which might be tempted to evade them because of its corporate nature, and the control of the public enterprise as a counter-power therefore seems to make good sense.

However, more than any other entity, today's public enterprise has two seemingly antagonistic objectives to pursue: the satisfaction of the general interest and the pursuit of profit. However, analysis shows that the State manages to reconcile these two aims by imposing the general interest as a public power and by taking into account the profitability of the public company by granting it greater management autonomy (Durupty M., 1984). The ultimate aim of controlling public enterprises is not to choose between these two objectives, but to channel the factors that influence them. This is where the new public management comes into play as a framework for applying management control to public enterprises.

Underperformance in the public sector was due to centralized bureaucracy, ineffective control mechanisms and wasteful use of available resources. These, then, are the problems that New Public Management is trying to tackle. New public management marks the transition from traditional public administration to new public management, an administration in which management control has a major role to play.

One of the primary aims of public enterprise control will be to make all the players and subjects of this control accountable (Chevalier J. and Lochak D., 1982). This starts with the State, whose duty it is to apply the regulations in force (requirement for transparency or clarity of rules and behavior), and ends with the public company, which will set up its own control system (good operation and efficiency). In terms of the State's responsibilities, it has the right to be held to account for the management of companies in which it has a majority stake. But control is also exercised at the heart of the company through audits and internal control systems.

These are just some of the means that need to be implemented within public companies to ensure the quality of management control within these structures. But alongside these resources, traditional and modern tools

must be mobilized on a daily basis to ensure this monitoring is effective and efficient. These include financial accounting, cost accounting, budgetary control, forecasting and budgetary management, reporting and, above all, the dashboard.

Based on the above literature, we framed the following hypothesis: *Public hospitals in Cameroon use modern management control tools*. The conceptual model associated to this hypothesis is depicted in the methodological aspects of this article.

2. METHODOLOGY

The theme of management control instrumentation in public institutions is not new in the world of management science research. In this work, we are applying the instrumentation of management control to a particular type of public institution, namely hospitals, which have their own specific characteristics. Based on the fact that we hope to cover the widest possible range of hospitals, we have chosen the quantitative approach as the methodological basis for this article.

2.1. Techniques and tools of data collection

For the data collection, we used our research hypothesis as a starting point to design an operationalization table to come out with our variables. This table highlighted the different indicators for the different dimensions of the data collection tools. This table is given below:

Table 1: Operationalization of variables

Hypothesis	Tools of MC	Dimensions	Indicateurs
Public hospitals in Cameroon use modern management control tools	Modern tools of management control: the BSC	Financial perspective	Monitoring financial info
			Monitoring operating costs
			Control of financial results
		Internal business process perspectives	Improved service quality
			On-time delivery
			Simplified procedures
		Learning and Growth perspectives	Realization of tasks
			Increased skills
			Risks mangement

Source: The authors, inspired by Kaplan & Norton (1996)

The table above highlights the main hypothesis that was tested in the empirical part of this work. We have formulated it as follows: *public hospitals in Cameroon use modern management control tools*.

To test this hypothesis, we designed a questionnaire based on the operationalization table above. This questionnaire enabled us to collect primary data from resource persons in the public hospitals surveyed. We present below the data analysis technique we used and the software employed.

2.2. Techniques and tools of data analysis

When analyzing the data, it should be remembered that we did not expect to disregard any variables measuring the various concepts and their dimensions. This is why we used structural equations. However, reliability analyses were also carried out to ensure the quality of the indicators used in the structural equation model.

The software we used is SmartPLS v.4. It enabled us to reconcile all the variables of our respective hypotheses simultaneously. It enabled us to highlight the regression coefficients of the conceptual models below:

Figure 1: Conceptual model of the use of modern management control tools

Source: The Authors

The conceptual model emphasizes the use of modern management control tools as instruments of this function within hospitals. The particularity of this hypothesis is that it contains several structural models. Modern management control tools have been split into three categories, namely the financial axis, the process axis and the organizational learning axis of the balanced scorecard. It should be remembered that we have disregarded the customer axis, as we are dealing with hospital establishments.

3. SURVEY RESULTS

3.1. Knowledge and practice of management control in Cameroonian hospitals

To assess knowledge of management control within hospitals in Cameroon, we used a multitude of indicators, two of which caught our attention. These were the essential nature of management control within hospitals and the existence of a management control department within them.

As far as the the essential nature of management control in Cameroon's hospital establishments, the following observations can be made:

Table 2: Management control is essential in hospital establishments (HE)

		Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Valid	Totally disagree	16	30,8	30,8	30,8
	Fairly agree	9	17,3	17,3	48,1
	Agree	27	51,9	51,9	100,0
	Total	52	100,0	100,0	

Source: The Authors

The table above shows that nearly 52% of respondents think that management control is essential for public HEs, while around 31% of Cameroonian respondents think that HEs do not need it; finally, 17% of them have a mixed view on the need for management control within HEs. In view of this fairly satisfactory finding, the results below show the situation with regard to the existence or non-existence of a management control department within these establishments:

Table 3: There exists a management control service within the targeted HEs

		Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Valid	Totally disagree	28	53,8	53,8	53,8
	Fairly agree	7	13,5	13,5	67,3
	Agree	17	32,7	32,7	100,0
	Total	52	100,0	100,0	

Source: The Authors

According to the table above, only around 33% of respondents are certain that they have a genuine management control department. On the other hand, more than 53% stated that management control is not deployed as an autonomous function in their EH; finally, almost 14% of respondents were dubious about the autonomous nature of the "Management Control" function within their hospital establishments.

3.2. Level of use of modern management control tools within Cameroonian hospitals

The choice of indicators for modern management control tools was based on the components of the Kaplan and Norton balanced scorecard. Of the four axes in this chart, only the customer axis was excluded, because in public hospitals (the target of the survey), we cannot speak of customers, but of users to be satisfied. On the other hand, the other three areas were assessed in our analysis. These are the financial axis, the internal processes axis and the learning and innovation axis. The situation in Cameroon is as follows:

Figure 2: The state of the use of modern management control tools in Cameroonian HEs

Source: The authors

From the diagram above, it can be seen that the contribution of modern management control tools to the practice of this discipline is represented by a coefficient of 0.702. This positive value, greater than 0.5, is the proof that modern tools are well used in Cameroon's public hospitals. The graph shows that the financial axis is predominant, with a coefficient of 0.801, followed by the internal processes axis, with a coefficient of 0.732, and the learning and innovation axis, with a coefficient of 0.698. These results show that **Cameroon's public hospitals are using modern management control tools**. Out hypothesis is therefore verified and validated.

4. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

While it is true that the financial axis has the highest score, it goes without saying that some of its indicators do not score as highly. This is particularly true of the "Q3.11" indicator representing growth in hospital revenues. Growth in hospital revenue is not a reality in Cameroon's public hospitals. While their ability to monitor financial information is improved with the use of the balanced scorecard as tool of management control. These hospitals are able to monitor and reduce operating costs with the help of the BSC, as it is also possible for them to control their financial results.

As far as internal business processes are concerned, the BSC makes many things possible to the targeted public hospitals. First, the quality of services has significantly improved. They are now able to meet healthcare delivery deadlines, since procedures are simplified and commitment and responsibility has

increased over time. This is the same for the learning axis where one can notice very scores for all the indicators.

As a matter of fact, workers say they feel more competent days after days. The use of the BSC clearly defines the role assigned to each and every one and makes job separation clear to everyone. They are therefore able to innovate in the way they carry out their various tasks. As a results, they have better control on the risks associated to their activities and they have fewer doubts when making choices and taking decisions.

On a theoretical point of view, the famous contribution of this article is that it underlines the necessity to go beyond the classical consideration of “traditional” management control tools (budgetary analysis, cost accounting, financial accounting), to integrate modern tools of management control like the balanced scorecard and reporting.

As far as the general hospitals are concerned, the Ministry of Finance has set up a budget monitoring unit, which is none other than the management controller. In the other entities, however, there is a management control body attached to general management. But the real specificity of public hospitals, especially the first category hospitals, is that the management control tools are provided for in the texts, but there is a lack of skills to implement these tools, both traditional and modern. For example, there is only one hospital that practices general accounting. Modern tools do exist, but not as management control tools, but as audit tools. So there is a mitigation in terms of expected results. The KPIs for these hospitals are not defined upstream. The advantage of our paper is that it raises awareness of the need to redefine the operational and structural performance objectives, review the profiles of the players and provide for appropriate posts in the organization charts, as these do not currently exist or are still under construction.

Since public hospitals in Cameroon have the legal status of public establishments, their mode of operation in terms of governance is guided by the provisions of certain laws and regulations, in particular the law on the financial regime of the State and other public entities. As a result, a management control manual has been drawn up by MINFI, defining management control and certain concepts that must be implemented within the entities, such as the management charter, management protocol, management dialogue and management charts. Our results show that the hospitals in question place particular emphasis on budget monitoring and internal procedures. The learning aspects are present but are not given much emphasis; hence the problem of competence highlighted by most of the respondents.

So, in 2007, the machinery of public finance reform was set in motion. The 2015 circular specifying the procedures for implementing management control in public establishments clarifies the role of management control as a tool for steering the performance of public hospitals. The tools used concern the strategic plan, the medium-term expenditure framework, resource projections, the annual work plan and the public hospital budget. This confirms that tools such as reporting and balanced scorecard are not mentioned as key management control tools in public hospitals. Their role is limited to assisting managers and monitoring the execution of the aforementioned activities. What is interesting, however, is that at the end of these monitoring activities, the management controller, under the supervision of the Chief Executive, monitors the implementation of the various tools mentioned above and draws up a performance report reconciling forecasts and actual figures.

CONCLUSION

The aim of this article was to assess the extent to which modern management control tools are used in Cameroon's public hospitals. In order to do this, we reviewed the essentials of the literature on the implementation of management control in public hospitals. Authors such as Chevalier J. and Loschak D., (1982) and Durupty M., (1984) made the task easy. After a sound literature review, we were able to enumerate most of the indicators of modern management control tools. And it appears that these indicators are mainly those of the balanced scorecard.

In a methodological building, we were able to operationalize these modern indicators into three categories derived from the BSC, namely: the financial perspective, the internal business process perspective and the learning and growth perspective. The methodological approach being the quantitative approach, we therefore built a questionnaire as data collection tool. The questionnaire helped us to collect data which was analyzed using the SPSS and SmartPLS software for the purpose of longitudinal analyses and structural equation modeling respectively.

The main result to which we arrived at is that of the validation of our main hypothesis. In other words, **Cameroon's public hospitals are using modern management control tools**. While the scores of the various indicators of all the axes of the balanced scorecard are high, only one indicator named "increased revenues" presents a fair but not so high coefficient. This situation serves as a foundation stone for our future investigations.

As per the contribution of the Balanced Scorecard (BSC) to Cameroonian general hospital, it offers a comprehensive framework to align their strategies with measurable performance indicators. By incorporating financial, customer, internal processes, and learning & growth perspectives, the BSC helps hospitals. It will help these hospitals improve operational efficiency by identifying and streamlining processes, reducing waste, and optimizing resource allocation, hospitals can enhance their operational efficiency and reduce costs. It will also contribute to align strategy to execution by providing a holistic view of performance, the BSC helps hospitals ensure that their actions are aligned with their strategic goals and objectives.

Beside all these positive contributions brought by these article's results, it also embodies some limitations good to mention. In Cameroon, there are five categories of general hospitals. But the results mentioned here are mainly those of the first two categories. The last three ones still have a long way to go as far as management control is concerned because of the lack of resources they face, the remoteness from urban areas and the people who get employed in these hospitals (they lack actualization). The results could have been depicted per category of general hospitals. The scope of the study could have been very large.

References

- Alfred, C. (1962), Strategy and structure: chapters in the history of the industrial enterprise, *Cambridge M.I.T Press*,
- Anthony, R. N. (1988). The Management Control Function. Boston: The Harvard Business School Press ;
- Avele, D.. et Bikourane, N. (2017), La mise en œuvre d'outil du contrôle de gestion et management de la performance en milieu hospitalier : une approche pour étude de cas dans les hôpitaux publics camerounais. ;
- Bouquin, H. (1994), Les Fondements du Contrôle de Gestion, Que sais-je?, PUF

-
- Chevalier, J. and Lochak D., (1982), *La science administrative*, Presses Universitaires de France, 2^{ème} édition, 108 Boulevard Saint-Germain, 75006 Paris ;
- Khemakhem, A. (1976), *La dynamique du contrôle de gestion*, Dunod, 2^{ème} édition, 587 pages ;
- Poyet, M. (2001), *Le Contrôle de l'Entreprise Publique : Essai sur le Cas Français*, Thèse de Doctorat, Université Jen Monnet, Saint-Etienne, Faculté de Droit ;
- Durupty, M. (1984), *La maîtrise de l'État sur les entreprises publiques*, *Revue Française d'Administration Publique*, n°20, pp. 95-118 ;
- Kaplan, R. S. & Norton, D. P. (1996), *Strategic learning and the balanced scorecard*, *Strategy & Leadership*, Vol. 24 No. 5, pp. 18-24. <https://doi.org/10.1108/eb054566> ;